

AN EVALUATION OF HYBRID LAMINATES USING ULTRA-HIGH MODULUS FIBER

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Abstract

This paper describes an investigation of hybrid laminates using ultra-high modulus (UHM) fibers motivated by the structural requirements for large spacecraft. Mechanical properties for both mature and recently developed pitch-based fiber composites are presented. Mechanical properties for hybrid laminates using UHM fibers and high-strength fibers are discussed. Fabrication methods for spaceframe truss members using the UHM materials are discussed, and the strengths of the various truss member configurations are presented.

Rationale for Investigation of Hybrid Laminates

Spacecraft structural design requirements are derived primarily from two sources: the payload that must be supported and the launch vehicle constraints (such as payload mass capability, payload envelope, and applied loads). Two themes have been apparent throughout the various large spacecraft design projects in which we have been involved: (1) large spacecraft tend to have stiffness-driven structures, and (2) the high cost of large launch

vehicles drives designs towards increasing payload-to-spacecraft weight fractions. In some instances, high-modulus composite structures become necessary for mission feasibility, being the only means of obtaining an adequately stiff structure within the allotted mass. In other cases, a composite structure may lead to the minimum-cost system by allowing use of a smaller, less expensive launch vehicle than would be required with a more conventional structure.

From September 1989 to February 1991, the authors were involved in designing a spacecraft with an inherently high-aspect-ratio (long and thin) payload intended to be launched on a commercial Titan (Figure 1). This configuration is a good example of a strongly performance-driven structural design. The weight of the payload and supporting subsystems consumed three quarters of the launch vehicle capability. The payload geometry led to a high-aspect-ratio cantilevered structure, even though the structure was placed outboard of the payload to obtain the largest diameter section possible. To avoid coupling with energetic launch vehicle vibration modes at liftoff, the first lateral bending mode frequency of the spacecraft had to be kept above 8 Hz.

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Fig. 1. Large Spaceframe Using Hybrid Laminate Composites

which is stiff for a structure of this size. These weight and stiffness requirements, coupled with unfavorable geometry, resulted in a highly performance-driven structure. To meet the challenging performance requirement, the structure was designed as a spaceframe using ultra-high modulus graphite/epoxy with bonded joints.

A spaceframe is the optimum structure for supporting a number of discrete payload elements. A skin and stringer concept was investigated to see if it offered a cost savings, but rough sizing indicated that this approach carried a 30% to 40% weight penalty, which we could not tolerate. This penalty is caused by two factors. First, the skin and stringer design places structural material away from the preferred load paths between the supported elements and the launch vehicle interface. Second, the panels are buckling-critical and so must be kept above a minimum gage.

For our geometry, primary structure weight was roughly proportional to the specific stiffness of the material. Figure 2 shows how the primary structure mass must be increased to meet a minimum natural frequency requirement. The required minimum frequency shown covers the range of typical launch vehicles. As can be seen from the figure, the

choice of material (aluminum, 75 Msi fiber composite, or 100 Msi fiber composite) strongly influences the amount of structural mass needed to meet any particular natural frequency. We investigated beryllium as well as various composite materials. Beryllium posed no insurmountable brittleness or safety hazard problems, but the estimated cost of the required beryllium tubes was over twice the cost of the equivalent set of graphite/epoxy tubes.

Carbon fibers are made from rayon, polyacrylonitrile (PAN), or pitch precursor materials. The most commonly used fibers for structural purposes are PAN-based. Pitch-based fibers can achieve as much as four times higher moduli than PAN-based fibers but have one-third the strengths and 30 times the cost. Composites fabricated with mesophase pitch fibers are typically referred to as ultra-high modulus composites.

Many potential ultra-high modulus carbon fibers were investigated. UHM fibers, including P100 and P120, have been commercially available for several years from Amoco Performance Products. The fibers have nominal tensile moduli of 110 and 120 Msi, respectively. A few Japanese companies have recently begun supplying UHM fibers

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Fig. 2. Mass versus Frequency

having higher strain-to-failure and strengths than the Amoco fibers with comparable stiffness. Among these fibers are FT700 from Tonen Energy Corporation and K139 and K13B from Mitsubishi Kasei. Table 1 shows the vendor-supplied properties for these UHM fibers. The manufacturer's fiber data indicate that P120 and K13B have the highest tensile modulus, K13B has the highest tensile strength, and FT700 has the highest ultimate elongation. These ultra-high modulus fibers were to be used for the on-axis fibers of a hybrid layup with off-axis fibers of a softer, stronger intermediate modulus material, such as Amoco's T650-42, for fabricability as detailed below.

Two basic approaches have been used for joining composites. A mechanically fastened joint can be made in metal reinforcements bonded into the basic composite structure, with joint weight penalties of 60% to 80%. All bonded joints are less forgiving of design flaws but carry smaller joint weight penalties (on the order of 25%) for a stiffness-critical structure. The weight criticality of the design required us to use an all-bonded joint configuration.

Joint design work indicated that the optimum tube cross-section from the joinability standpoint was one with flat faces for bonding simple splice plates. We planned to use square tubes for battens and diagonal members. A more complex longeron cross section, as shown in Figure 1, was selected to present splicing surfaces to adjacent members in two planes. Because the UHM fibers do not lend themselves to being formed around the corners of these faceted cross-sections without fiber breakage, we planned to use intermediate-modulus PAN-based carbon fibers for the off-axis fibers. The spaceframe member axial stiffness is primarily provided by the on-axis (0-deg) fibers while the off-axis fibers provide the necessary strength to keep the laminate from failing in local shear. We ran the off-axis fibers at ±45 deg to maximize shear-carrying performance. The hybrid ultra-high modulus/intermediate-modulus fiber mix places each fiber where its particular properties can best be utilized. The resulting mix is also less expensive than a pure ultra-high modulus fiber composite. We began by using proportions of about 67% ultra-high modulus fibers to 33% intermediate-modulus fibers based on previous composite spaceframe designs. We had begun an optimization analysis to select the best layup and may have been able to use a higher percentage of on-axis fibers due to our structure design being highly stiffness-driven.

We did not make a final decision on the best fabrication approach, which would tend to drive the matrix selection.

Leading candidates were pultrusion and mandrel wrapping with external dies. Other approaches, such as filament winding, were investigated but appeared less promising for our application. We were leaning toward processes that would produce tubes with good control of outside dimensions to allow easy splicing. A fabrication method that did not provide this tight outer mold line control would have to be very inexpensive to offset the cost of local shimming on assembly at the joints.

Hybrid Laminate Coupon Tests

To validate this design approach and to develop data for detailed design analysis, we conducted coupon tests and tube fabrication development tests. In an effort to verify the relative performance of ultra-high modulus fibers, and to establish a set of design properties, flat specimens were tested. The coupons were made from hybrid laminates consisting of 67% UHM plies in the 0-deg direction and 33% intermediate-modulus plies in the ±45-deg directions. Coupon tests were performed to determine mechanical and thermophysical properties.

The UHM fibers tested were P120 from Amoco Performance Products, K139 and K13B from Mitsubishi Kasei, and FT700 from Tonen. A variety of resin systems were also tested: ICI Fiberite's 934 epoxy, 977-2 toughened epoxy, and 954-3 cyanate ester and Amoco's ERL 1939-3, a modified cyanate resin. Amoco supplied data from its own tests on a laminate made with its P100 fiber and ERL 1962 epoxy resin. The intermediate-modulus fibers used for off-axis layers were Toray T800 for the laminates made with the Japanese fibers and T650-42 for the Amoco laminate. Table 2 lists the layups, fibers, and resins for all the panels tested.

The tests included mechanical and physical properties testing, as well as coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) testing. The mechanical tests included: tensile modulus and strength; compression modulus and strength; in-plane shear

Table 2. UHM Hybrid Laminates Tested

Panel no.	Layup	Axial (0-deg) fiber	Off-axis fiber	Resin
1	(0 ₂ /+45/0/-45/0) ₃	FT700	T800	934
2	(0 ₂ /+45/0/-45/0) ₃	FT700	T800	954-3
3	(0 ₂ /+45/0/-45/0) ₃	K139	T800	934
4	(0 ₂ /+45/0/-45/0) ₃	K139	T800	954-3
5	(0/+45/0 ₂ /-45/0) ₂₃	P100	T650-42	ERL 1962

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Table 1. Vendor-Supplied Properties of Selected Ultra-High Modulus Carbon Fibers

Fiber properties	Amoco P100	Amoco P120	Mitsubishi K139	Mitsubishi K13B	Tonen FT700
Tensile modulus (Msi)	110	120	107	120	100
Tensile strength (ksi)	350	350	400	514	470
Ultimate elongation (%)	0.32	0.29	0.37	0.43	0.5
CTE (ppm/°F)	-0.8	-0.8	-0.8	-0.8	-0.8
Density (lb/in ³)	0.078	0.079	0.077	0.078	0.078

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modulus and strength; short-beam shear strength. All mechanical property specimens were moisture conditioned prior to testing, and all were performed at room temperature. Physical properties determined were laminate density, fiber volume fraction, void content, and resin content. Five replications were performed for each mechanical property test, and three replications were performed for each of the other tests. Table 3 lists all the tests performed and, where appropriate, the applicable ASTM or SACMA specification. All specimen machining, preparation, and testing was performed at independent laboratories.

The results of the hybrid laminate coupon tests, including the Amoco test data on the P100 hybrid laminate, are summarized in Table 4. The table includes average values and standard deviations for each test type. The tension, compression, and in-plane shear data are normalized to a fiber volume of 60%. Tensile strength is plotted versus compression strength in Figure 3. The data indicate that the FT700 and K139 laminates have significantly higher tensile strengths than the P100 laminate but roughly the same compression strength. The strengths of the FT700 laminates were different for the two different resin systems: the laminate with the 954-3 cyanate ester had a 15% higher tensile strength, and the laminate with the 934 epoxy had a 45% higher compression strength. No such difference was observed for the K139 laminates. A plot of tensile versus compression modulus is shown in Figure 4. The tensile modulus of the P100 laminate was about the same as the

Fig. 3. Hybrid Laminate Tensile versus Compression Strength

other laminates, but the compression modulus was lower. For both the FT700 and K139 laminates, the compression modulus was higher for the laminates with the cyanate ester resin—13% higher for FT700 and 16% higher for K139.

Laminate stiffness and strength properties were predicted using a laminate analysis computer program based on classical lamination theory. For strength predictions, a maximum stress failure model with a first-ply failure criteria was used. Although the tensile and compression modulus predictions were all within 13%, the errors in the tensile and

Table 3. Coupon Tests Performed on Flat Laminates

Test type	Properties	Specification	Comments
0-deg tension	E_x, ν_{xy}, F_x (tension)	ASTM D3039	
0-deg compression	E_x, ν_{xy}, F_x (compression)	SACMA SRM 1-88	Boeing-type specimen
In-plane shear	G_{xy}, F_{xy}	—	Iosipescu
Short-beam shear	F_{x3}	ASTM D2344	
Physical properties	V_f, V_v, π	ASTM D3171 ASTM D792 ASTM D2734	
CTE	α_x	ASTM E 831-86	-250°F to +250°F
Bolt bearing	F_{br}	—	Double lap

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Table 4. Coupon Test Results for Hybrid Laminates

Property		FT700,T800/ 934	FT700,T800/ 954-3	K139,T800/ 934	K139,T800/ 954-3	P100, T650-42 1962
Tensile strength (ksi)	Average	131.5	151.1	120.7	122.2	89.3
	Std deviation	9.58	5.29	5.04	14.6	6.99
Tensile modulus (Msi)	Average	41.8	40.7	43.2	45.9	43.5
	Std deviation	0.84	0.72	1.61	2.79	0.83
Compression strength (ksi)	Average	50.7	34.9	37.8	37.5	36.1
	Std deviation	3.65	2.23	2.2	2.74	—
Compression modulus (Msi)	Average	40.8	46.1	43.1	49.9	37.5
	Std deviation	4.44	5.35	0.71	1.18	—
In-plane shear strength (Msi)	Average	22.3	21.7	20.4	22.4	21.1
	Std deviation	1.06	1.34	1.65	0.51	—
In-plane shear modulus (Msi)	Average	2.0	1.7	2.2	2.2	3.0
	Std deviation	0.16	0.21	0.35	0.08	—
Short beam shear strength (ksi)	Average	6.67	6.22	6.37	6.20	5.24
	Std deviation	0.07	0.3	0.22	0.23	—

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Fig. 4. Hybrid Laminate Tensile versus Compression Modulus

compression strength predictions were generally about twice as large. The errors in the in-plane shear property predictions were also around 25% for both stiffness and strength. These large errors may have been caused by any or all of the following: inaccuracies in the laminate failure model, inaccurate values for the laminate unidirectional properties used in the model, and experimental error.

Truss Member Fabrication Studies

Fabricating an efficient UHM truss structure at a reasonable cost presents several challenges, primarily because of the inherent properties of the UHM fibers. The same process that makes these fibers extremely stiff also makes them brittle and expensive. Although hand layup techniques could be used to fabricate the truss members, with postfabrication machining operations performed to custom-fit the members together, this approach is extremely labor-intensive and therefore very costly. Traditional approaches for automated fabrication of uniform high-quality composite parts such as filament winding and pultrusion have worked well for parts made from PAN-based carbon fibers, which are typically stronger and have a much higher strain-to-failure than the UHM fibers. But neither these nor any other viable automated fabrication method has been demonstrated for very large UHM primary structures.

One of the objectives of this study was to evaluate the suitability of filament winding and pultrusion for fabrication of truss members for UHM structures similar to the octagonal truss shown in Figure 1. The cross-section of a typical member fabricated for this study is shown in Figure

5. The members have a side dimension of 3 in., an internal corner radius of 0.25 in., and a wall thickness of approximately 0.06 in. For the application of interest, filament winding is the more mature of the two methods, but pultrusion, which requires more development, may have a greater payoff. To fabricate a truss member by the method of pultrusion, a knitted UHM preform with the proper layup is used. Initial efforts have focused on pultruding flat strips. With truss member fabrication expected to begin in early 1993. Meanwhile, a filament winding study has produced several UHM truss members.

A total of four truss members were fabricated from a variety of materials using hand layup and/or filament winding techniques to investigate the viability of filament winding UHM truss members. Table 5 lists the layup, materials, and fabrication method for each of the members. Details of the fabrication procedure are as follows:

A. The first member, which was to serve as a baseline for comparison to the other members, consisted of P120/1939-3 for the axial plies and IM7/8551-7A for the bias plies. The IM7 fiber is a high-strength, intermediate-modulus PAN-based carbon fiber, and the 8551-7A resin is a toughened, 350°F curing epoxy; both are manufactured by Hercules. External caul plates were made by laying up and curing fiberglass/epoxy cloth over a dummy part with the

Fig. 5. Truss Member Cross-Section

Table 5. Truss Members Fabricated from Ultra-High Modulus Materials

ID	Layup	Material	Fabrication Method
1	$[0_2 / \pm 45/0_2]_s$	P120/1939-3 (0-deg plies) IM7/8551-7A (± 45 -deg plies)	Hand layup
2	$[0_2 / \pm 45/0_2]_s$	K139/977-2 (0-deg plies) AS4/3501 (± 45 -deg plies)	Hand layup (0-deg plies) Filament wound (± 45 -deg plies)
3	$[0_2 / \pm 45/0_2]_s$	FT700/934	Hand layup
4	$[\pm 10 / \pm 45 / \pm 10]_s$	FT700/Epoxy	Wet-filament wound

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expected dimensions of the actual finished part. The caul plates were split into two pieces, each with a 90-deg angle cross-section. The purpose of the caul plates was to produce a smooth, uniform external surface. The P120 and IM7 prepreg was laid up entirely by hand over an aluminum internal mandrel. The part and associated tooling were vacuum-bagged and autoclave-cured at a maximum temperature of 350°F and a maximum pressure of 100 psig.

B. The second member was made with K139/977-2 for the axial plies and AS4/3501 for the bias plies. The AS4 fiber is a high-strength, intermediate-modulus PAN-based carbon fiber, and the 3501 resin is a standard 350°F curing epoxy; both are from Hercules. The purpose of this member was to demonstrate a semi-automated fabrication approach. The axial plies were laid up by hand, and the bias plies were laid up by winding 0.3 in.-wide towpreg. Pins were used to facilitate turnaround at the ends of the part. The same mandrel and external tooling used for the first member were used for this member, which was vacuum-bagged and cured in a manner similar to that used for the first member.

C. The third truss member was fabricated to determine whether or not the UHM material could be laid up at ± 45 deg over the corners without damaging the fibers. This member was made entirely of FT700/934. FT700 was selected because it has the highest ultimate elongation of all the UHM fibers investigated in this study. All plies were laid up by hand over the aluminum mandrel. The tooling, bagging, and cure cycle were similar to those used for the other two tubes. The all-UHM member was successfully fabricated without any detectable damage to the fibers. Experiments were also made toward laying up tubes with the more brittle Amoco materials as off-axis fibers. These efforts were discontinued because fiber damage was visible to the naked eye when these fibers were bent over the edge of the mandrel.

D. Finally, the fourth member was made to demonstrate a low-cost, fully automated fabrication approach. This member was made by wet-filament-winding FT700 fiber onto an aluminum mandrel with pins on either end to facilitate fiber turnaround. The fiber was passed through a resin bath and metered with a doctor blade to control resin content. The resin used was a standard 350°F curing epoxy. The axial plies in the layup were changed to ± 10 -deg plies to facilitate the winding operation. Fiberglass caul plates were placed on the external surface of the part, and shrink tape was wound over the plates. The member was autoclave-cured at 350°F and 85 psig. A visual inspection of the member found slight wrinkling in the corner regions and, overall, a dry (resin-poor) surface.

E. Resin content, void content, fiber volume, and wall thickness were determined for each member; the members were also ultrasonic-inspected. The results indicated that the properties of the first three members were within the specified range for resin content of $32 \pm 2\%$ by weight and void content of less than 2% by volume.

However, the average resin content of the fourth member was only 17.9%. The very low resin content of the fourth member was attributed to improper metering of the resin during the winding operation. The corner wrinkles in this member should also be easily eliminated by modifying the external tooling.

The fabrication study demonstrated that (1) towpreg-winding bias plies of PAN-based fibers is a viable method for partially automating the fabrication of hybrid truss members, (2) FT700 in prepreg form can be successfully used for the bias plies, (3) it is possible to produce a truss member from FT700 entirely by wet-filament winding, and (4) more development work is required to make an acceptable UHM truss member by wet-filament winding.

Truss Member Compression Tests

Achieving optimum structural properties from a composite truss member is more difficult than it is for a flat laminate simply because the geometry of the truss member is more complex. It is more difficult to get uniform compaction pressure, and hence uniform resin and fiber distribution, and low void content. Furthermore, the likelihood of fiber damage occurring during fabrication increases as the geometry of the part becomes more complex. This is especially true for truss member 3, for which the UHM material was used for the bias as well as the axial plies. Even though no damage was detected from visual and ultrasonic inspections, it was hypothesized that some microscopic damage may have been induced in the corner regions of this member during fabrication, which could reduce its strength and/or stiffness.

Compression test specimens were designed for truss members 1, 2, and 3 to determine the structural properties of the members. A sketch of the specimens is shown in Figure 6. The gage length of the specimens was 4 in. Fiberglass/epoxy cloth was added to the ends of the specimens on both the inner and outer surfaces to prevent failure near the ends. The thickness of the buildups was tapered from 0.066 in. at the end caps to 0.022 in. near the middle of the specimens. The ends were machined flat and perpendicular to the specimen axes to within 0.005 in. to minimize eccentricities in the loading. The ends of the specimens were then cast into grooved aluminum blocks with a room-temperature curing epoxy resin, and the blocks were machined, as required, to the same tolerance for flatness and perpendicularity. A total of four axially oriented strain gages were placed on the outside surface of the specimens in the center of each face. The gages were numbered sequentially from one to four around the circumference of the specimens. Three specimens from each of the three truss members were made. Unfortunately, one of the FT700 specimens was damaged during machining and could not be tested.

A finite element model of the specimen was used to determine the proper specimen dimensions. The ends of the

Fig. 6. Specimens for Truss Member Compression Tests

specimens were assumed to be fully constrained except for the axial degree of freedom at one end where a uniform axial load was applied. Specimens with different gage lengths and end buildup dimensions were modeled to determine the proper parameters to produce a material compression failure near the center of the faces. The specimen was made long enough to minimize end effects, yet short enough to preclude buckling failure. The axial length, thickness, and taper of the buildups were chosen to achieve a smooth transition in load from the ends of the specimens to the center. Figure 7 shows the finite element model results for axial stress over the middle portion of the specimen (i.e., the portion with no buildups) subject to an axial compression load of 40 kip. The portion of the model shown in the figure represents one-fourth of the total cross-section. Notice that the highest stress is in the middle portion of the sides, and that the stress in the corners is only 8% lower. This means that if the corner material is slightly weaker than the rest of the specimen, then failure will occur in the corners.

The specimens were loaded at a rate of approximately 20 kip/minute until failure. Strain gage data were recorded for the duration of the tests. Typical strain-versus-load plots for each of the three types of specimens are shown in Figures 8 through 10. Because they are not coincident, the curves indicate some nonuniformity in the loading and/or stiffness of the four sides. The strain gage data indicate that the P120 specimens experienced abrupt compression failure without any bending of the sides. However, some of the faces of the other specimens either bowed out or in prior to failure, as

evidenced by the rapid increase (inward deflection) or decrease (outward deflection) of the strain just below the failure load. Although the finite element model predicts that the sides will bow outward slightly when the specimen is compressed, it is believed that the faces may have been slightly concave, which would cause the sides to bow

Fig. 7. Finite Element Results for Axial Stress in Middle Portion of Truss Member Compression Specimen

Fig. 8. Strain Gage Curves for P120-IM7 Truss Member Compression Specimen

Fig. 10. Strain Gage Curves for FT700 Truss Member Compression Specimen

inward instead. In general, the specimens failed at mid-span all the way around the circumference.

Table 6 lists the results from the tests as well as predictions for the failure load. The predicted failure load was calculated from the finite element model results assuming the specimen fails when the maximum allowable stress in a given ply is exceeded. Vendor-supplied material properties were used in the models. The percentage error in the predictions, calculated as the actual failure load subtracted from the predicted load, divided by the actual load, is also listed in the table. The predicted failure load was significantly greater than the actual load in all cases. Inaccuracies in the model (including material properties), nonuniform loading of the specimen, and degradation of mechanical properties as a result of the fabrication process may all have contributed to the discrepancy between predicted and actual failure loads. Although there is not a one-to-one correspondence between the flat laminates and the tubes, the stress levels in the tube walls at the failure load can be compared to those of the flat laminate for tube No.

Fig. 9. Strain Gage Curves for K139-AS4 Truss Member Compression Specimen

2. The failure stress level for tube No. 2 of 36 ksi can be compared to the 37.8 ksi failure level of the flat K139 hybrid laminate.

Conclusions

UHM composites offer significant advantages over conventional composites and metals in terms of structural efficiency. To realize maximum benefit from UHM composites for large structures with demanding specific stiffness requirements, a data base on these materials must be established. This study has evaluated several UHM composites, including products from domestic and foreign suppliers. Coupon test data provide information on the properties of hybrid laminates made from UHM and intermediate-modulus materials. The data indicate differences in the strength and stiffness properties of the different UHM materials, as well as differences in performance between laminates made with cyanate ester and epoxy resins. Fabrication studies for UHM truss members indicate that filament winding may be a viable approach to reduce fabrication costs relative to the costs of hand layup. Results from compression tests on the truss members indicate that compression strength can be similar to that achieved in a flat laminate. Further work is required to produce high-strength tubes with automated fabrication methods.

Table 6. Truss Member Compression Test Results

ID	1	2	3
Material, 0-deg plies	P120/1939-3	K139/977-2	FT700/934
Material, ±45-deg plies	IM7/8551-7A	AS4/3501	FT700/934
Failure load (kip)	24.77 24.14 22.58	26.97 27.06 25.90	— 19.75 18.60
Average failure load (kip)	22.58	26.64	19.31
Predicted failure load (kip)	27.48	33.69	23.51
Error (%)	15.3	26.5	21.8
Failure stress (ksi)	32.2	36.0	26.1

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